

YES, YOU CAN!
STRONGER
FARMERS, A MORE
DEVELOPED AGRI-
FOOD SECTOR,
FAIRER EUROPEAN
ECONOMIES

agr.
BRIDGES

INTRODUCTION

Europe's fast-growing industrialisation, long-distance transportation, urbanisation, and technical advances facilitated the increase of mass distribution during the last half century, offering benefits and more comfortable purchasing behaviours for end-users; however, this development had consequences on individual producers' bargaining power, unbalancing their position in the agri-food supply chain and decreasing their income.

Reignited by recent consumer trends, lower waste generation, better product quality alternatives, and a renewed consumer interest in direct purchasing has led to the

resurgence of Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) (EIP-AGRI Focus Group Innovative Short Food Supply Chain management. , 2015). Nevertheless, the potential demand is far from being fulfilled as there is still a lot of room for growth and competitiveness. This is related to a lack of cooperation among farmers, the generation gap, distribution systems, the seasonal character of production and underdeveloped marketing techniques and infrastructure to boost the added value of local food.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Different types of SFSCs often struggle due to the small existing workforce. In an effort to compensate for this, those running the business will attempt to regularly multitask daily activities, which can lead to “burnout” (Kneafsey et al., 2013). To overcome this shared challenge, the need for collaboration amongst SFSC actors is crucial, as the relationship among actors in creating value plays an important role in SFSC development. Lack of trust between actors due to a shortage of communication platforms to exchange experiences, and the complexity in finding potential partners with common goals can undermine the cooperative spirit and the likelihood of building collaborative ventures (Kvam and Bjørkhaug, 2015).

The European Commission (EC) has highlighted the issue of lack of cooperation skills and low levels of smart organisation among farmers (The European Commission, 2013). Joining collaborative initiatives and keeping up the motivation of key actors can be tough (Galli and Brunori, 2013; Mount et al., 2013), as divisions among different interest groups to define the underlying direction of short food chains are frequently illustrated, and lead to hampering collaboration between

producers (Hassanein, 2003; Ribeiro et al., 2020). Managing internal dynamics, power relations, and dominant voices is at times problematic and can often stifle the innovation and growth of SFSCs (Kirwan et al., 2013).

The EC is aiming to support the global transition to sustainable agri-food systems through its trade policies and international cooperation instruments to accelerate the transition to fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food systems. Supports such as advisory services, financial instruments and Research & Innovation programs to develop test solutions, overcome barriers and release new market opportunities are available.

Among the most relevant advisory services to be deployed are cooperation initiatives, such as documenting and sharing good practices, that are expected to allow SFSCs actors to learn from the experience of others via peer-to-peer learning and to use this knowledge to increase their capacity. If Good Practice reports are undervalued, successful experiences might be overlooked and opportunities for improved practices may be lost, which can lead to a lack of replication.

AIM OF THE agroBRIDGES SUCCESS CASES

Aiming to overcome the barriers outlined earlier (addressed in detail in the agroBRIDGES report on European and regional analysis of producer and consumer needs and barriers), awareness and training are essential for producers to learn about SFSC particularities and successful SFSC practices, as well as to acquire valuable knowledge that can inspire replication of those success cases and promote cooperation and sharing initiatives among them.

According to FAO (2013) a “good practice” is not only a practice that is good but is a practice that has been proven to work well and produce good results; and is therefore recommended as a model. The purpose of this white paper is to illustrate the best-in-class practices that were identified during co-creation workshops of the agroBRIDGES project, to outline guidelines on how to leverage them, and to act as motivation to strengthen farmers’ position in the food value chain.

Benefits that this whitepaper brings:

- Discover and be inspired by the main key takeaways through this sorted list of success cases.
- A storytelling approach to feel better identified with any of the cases.
- Raising awareness about the huge potential to scale-up own initiatives.

Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) are increasingly expanding in recent decades, driven by producers’ eagerness to improve their market position, consumers’ concern about finding nearby, healthy and fairly priced food, as well as innovative policies aimed at making the regional and local food system more resilient and sustainable.

SFSCs are evolving differently in the European Union across different areas and therefore capturing a broad selection of the critical success factors of good practices will not only embrace each of the main types of SFSCs but also the key drivers to adopt them in a variety of different contexts, making them easily replicable by a wide range of SFSC actors. Through the agroBRIDGES research and activities, a set of 4 different regions have been addressed to point out the most successful cases for replication:

- In the Mediterranean, open-air markets have combined producer direct sales, with retailers who generally market both short and long-chain products. The presence of producers in covered markets has been reduced due to the crisis of these facilities or their conversion into gastronomic spaces linked to gourmet products, restaurants, and other types of specialised shops. For this reason, some initiatives call for a relaunch of markets as public places as well as community services that promote a circular economy.

- In North-West Europe, farmers' markets have been embracing open-air sales since the 1970s, with the successful participation of producers and government support.

- In Eastern Europe, local sourcing, in different formats, still maintains an important presence, combining self-consumption and social gardens. Both indoor and outdoor markets exist, along with embryonic Community Supported Agriculture and km0 sourcing initiatives.

- In the Scandinavian and Baltic countries, an effervescent gastronomic sector bases its proposals on proximity production, fostering virtuous circles of collaboration.

SOLUTION

This white paper is expected to collect and illustrate specific case studies gathered from different European countries to highlight that robust business models can be created using different approaches to prove that SFSCs are crucial to triggering connections between producers and consumers and therefore strengthen farmers' position in European markets. Throughout this white paper, 12 success cases of differing SFSCs will be showcased to highlight their social, economic, and environmental impacts on their local communities. Furthermore, geographical diversity across the European countries will be reflected by identifying the different types of SFSC business models and outlining the valuable and positive impact on the area. Three main themes explored are:

Mutually beneficial between primary producers and consumers of SFSCs.

Good practices that provide benefits to both the general public and food producers were targeted to eventually create win-win situations; the greater the frequency of face-to-face interactions between consumers and producers, the more trustful and transparent the cooperation is. These face-to-face interactions enhance the market knowledge of the producers, by better understanding consumers' preferences via seamless feedback. Another example of mutual benefits is provided by a farmers' market. This type of sales point provides consumers access to an array of fresh and seasonal local food in one location. Additionally, producers are provided with a place to sell their produce directly to consumers and therefore enjoy economic benefits, and greater autonomy than would be found in conventional supply chains.

Education and awareness-raising practices.

Good Practices include public education as well as practices that increase general awareness of SFSCs and their unique benefits. Marketing involves efforts to increase the profile of SFSCs and can include branding and labelling among other approaches. Education and awareness efforts focus on increasing consumer awareness of the benefits of shorter supply chains, as well as where and when to attain food produced from SFSCs.

Public procurement SFSCs approaches for offices, schools, and hospitals.

Good Practices about public procurement include public sector support for SFSCs. Local authorities can promote food procurement via SFSCs for entities such as schools or hospitals. For example, public procurement legislation can explicitly allow, or even require, the inclusion of local food in public calls for tenders.

Hypothetical examples of Good Practice related to each theme

<p>Mutual benefits between primary producers and consumers in SFSCs</p>	<p>Education and awareness raising practices</p>	<p>Public procurement SFSCs approaches for offices, schools, hospitals, etc.</p>
<p>SFSCs that offer better access to a range of fresh, seasonal and high-quality foods.</p>	<p>The organisation of social events (e.g. farm visits) with the aim of connecting farmers and consumers to improve mutual understanding and to foster trust.</p>	<p>Public procurement guidelines that aim to foster the provision of food through SFSCs in public organisations</p>
<p>Support of the local economy by providing both direct and indirect employment while also ensuring that money stays within a region.</p>	<p>Communicating with consumers to promote and share knowledge about products, processing, farming practices, etc.</p>	<p>Cooperation and coordination among food producers in food logistics and provisions.</p>
<p>Increase face-to-face interaction of farmers with consumers that results in higher levels of consumer trust. Consumers appreciate the increased transparency and traceability associated with SFSCs.</p>	<p>Education initiatives and campaigns that aim to enhance consumer perceptions of local food</p>	<p>Regulation that specifies that at least a certain proportion of food provided for meals in public institutions must be directly sourced from SFSCs.</p>

1. AIRFIELD (DUBLIN, IRELAND)

Description

Built around a 38-acre estate encompassing farmland, woodland, a farm shop, a farmers' market, an award-winning restaurant, gardens, the original family home and associated buildings, this not-for-profit organisation provides a range of services and activities to raise awareness and provide education to many target groups.

Following a methodology based on 4 strategic pillars, they ensure that consumers understand the impact of their food choices on themselves, their families, society as a whole and, ultimately, the planet. These 4 pillars are:

- A) **Sustain Pillar** – Airfield as a valuable resource to fund charitable activities.
- B) **Connect Pillar** - Use food data & tech solutions to nudge the consumer to make food choices that benefit people, planet & pocket.

C) **Engage Pillar** - Increase their reach and impact through accessible online and community engagement.

D) **Collaborate Pillar** - Work with other food-related charities to grow their reach and impact.

Airfield Estate uses their working farm as a backdrop for education and awareness activities suitable for all ages. This ensures a hands-on, interactive, fun way of learning. Working with partners, such as the Teachers Council, informs the design of the programme, provides confidence to parents and others looking for such activities and a channel to potential end-users. They also leverage the UK-based charity LEAF programme 'Farmer Time' to access a digital platform to connect teachers, children, and farmers. Children regularly interact with farm life, from their classrooms, with their matched farmers through this digital platform. This enables them to ask questions, share knowledge and gain a 'real-time' understanding of the issues that farmers/producers face every day.

Theme

Mutually beneficial between primary producers and consumers SFSCs

Sector

Meat, fruit and vegetables, bakery, dairy

IT

a) Online digital engagement platform to connect farmers with school children via [LEAF](#) and b) [Evocco](#) – A tracker tool to help consumers make more sustainable food choices.

Actors

Teaching Council, LEAF, INDI (Irish Nutritional Dieticians Association)

Benefits

An annual membership scheme provides an incentive for members to engage in lifelong learning about food and seasonality, for themselves and their families. Awareness-raising and education activities are "hands-on" as much as possible.

agroBRIDGES insight

Jennifer Attard from MTU quoted *“Airfield is a fantastic business because it not only provides a sustainable option for food, but continuously strives to encourage more individuals to understand the benefits of sustainable food systems. Children are the future, so fun, interactive methods that encourage a sustainable mindset are key to a sustainable future.”*

2. BIOVALVERDE (SEVILLE, SPAIN)

Description

A non-profit and inclusion company promoted by Cáritas Diocesana de Sevilla. They pursue the inclusion of people in or at risk of social exclusion, as well as raise awareness and increase fair and sustainable consumption, by the exploitation, among other business areas, of an ecological farm of 30 hectares, the cooperation with other ecological farmers and the distribution of the product with a proximate SFSC approach.

90% of the products sold are grown/produced in the region, and 100% of them have a national and ecological origin. To ensure a stable and wide variety of products, and a win-win approach through the value system that could ensure the client's fidelity and farmer's profitability, BIOALVERDE:

- a) produces and sells its products,
- b) buys products from other ecological farmers,
- c) cooperates with other proximate distributors, to ensure the sale of all products and to avoid the food waste.

Theme

Mutually beneficial between primary producers and consumers SFSCs

Sector

Vegetables

IT

E- commerce shop: [Inicio](#) | [Bioalverde \(mientidad.com\)](#)

Actors

Local Farmers, Charity, Non-profit associations, Consumers

Benefits

The consumption model of society leads us to a situation of poverty and exclusion. Bioalverde follows the principles of the Social and Solidarity Economy, which puts people, the environment and sustainable development first. The economy can be humanised and BIOALVERDE is proving it: they are changing the values that have led us to this situation. They promote a transformative initiative, capable of putting people at the centre.

It is important to become aware of the transformative power that our choices have on the different products we consume. Demanding products that come from processes that respect people's rights and the environment and leading a sustainable lifestyle are necessary steps to confront exclusion and conserve all-natural resources.

1) BIOALVERDE builds tailor-made plans in collaboration with each farmer to know exactly the timeline of

production for each product, the possibilities of storage and the logistics needed for distributing the product in better conditions.

2) BIOALVERDE is creating a network of similar proximity SFSC initiatives that could ensure an economy of scale to guarantee the profitability of the farmers. They combine to match the production calendar and volumes with the potential demand to decide if it's viable to grow a product.

3) BIOALVERDE considers that a proximity approach must be also considered in all the communication and dissemination activities towards the consumers, including physical events, visits to the production fields, cooking activities, etc. They capitalize on any opportunity they have to bring together their farmers and the consumers.

agroBRIDGES insight

Victor Corral from CTA quoted *"BIOALVERDE is a clear example of how to merge the objectives of the socio-occupational integration of people in a situation or at risk of social exclusion, as well as promoting fair, sustainable, ecological and responsible consumption, through short food supply chains, by raising people's awareness. It is promoting the principles of the Social and Solidarity Economy, which puts people, the environment and sustainable development first."*

3. FRU MOLLERS MOLLERI (DENMARK)

Description

Fru Møllers Mølleri is characterised by having a very wide range of products and experiences for the consumer. On the farm, there is a mill, farm shop, ice-cream parlour and restaurant. On the shelves are handmade goods based on raw materials from their agricultural production. They grow and grind their own grain. The slow-moving stone grinder ensures flour that is filled with nutrients and has the perfect baking ability. They produce and sell freshly ground flour. Since 2007, they have been inviting guests into the Farm Shop where they find local products and selected goods from other parts of the country. You can also attend a cooking class and cook based on seasonal local ingredients as well as buy products on their webshop. Fru Møllers Mølleri has been a leader in Denmark to create an overall concept for production, processing, farm sales, and experiences for customers that can attract both locals and people from far and wide as well as tourists. It has become a well known excursion destination.

Theme

Mutually beneficial between primary producers and consumers SFSCs

Sector

Meat, Fruit and Vegetables, cereals, bakery.

IT

Webshop:

<https://frumollersmolleridk/shop/>

Actors

Food producers, distributors, consumers.

Benefits

Fru Møllers Mølleri was one of the first in Denmark to create an overall concept for production, processing, farm sales and experiences for customers. There are a total of 32 employees (17 FTE). Fru Møllers Mølleri has helped to create interest among consumers in locally produced raw materials. Consumers can buy locally produced and processed quality products in one place and at the same time get an experience. It attracts both locals and people from far and wide as well as tourists. It has become an excursion destination. They have managed to create a combination of farm shops and tourist attractions. Consumers make a trip to Fru Møllers Mølleri to have an experience while buying local products.

agroBRIDGES insight

Britt Sandvad, from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark, quoted *“Fru Møllers Mølleri is a really good example of an initiative that combines the sale of local products with giving the customer an experience. Visiting Fru Møllers Mølleri is not just about shopping - here all senses are catered for and the visit is an experience in itself.*”

4. KINDERGARTEN “DUZGYNELIS” (VILNIUS, LITHUANIA)

Description

Kindergarten "Duzgynelis" is the first private kindergarten in Vilnius (Lithuania) established in an individual house, with a small, enclosed courtyard, and near the forest to create a cosy, warm, healthy, natural oasis to grow food for children. Small groups, daily production of fresh food, individual attention, upholding forgotten values, and developing a healthy lifestyle are some of the core values of the kindergarten. Their SFSC model is based on buying organic food from farmers and selling it to the parents of kindergarten children, as well as producing food from organic products and supplying food and organic products to other kindergartens. Kindergarten-baked organic bread has become popular among the surrounding residents of the district, so bread and bread products are also available to the general public.

Theme

Mutually beneficial between primary producers and consumers SFSCs and Education and awareness-raising practices

Sector

All Sectors

IT

Website [Duzgynelis](#) and social media.

Actors

Farmers, local consumers, kindergarten, children

Benefits

Consumers (parents) can buy healthy products while picking up their children. The kindergarten is also a producer and distributor of their own food products to other kindergartens and the general public.

Health and ecological awareness building among children and parents. The novel business model is in line with sustainability and nature. A bridge between farmers and consumers.

agroBRIDGES insight

Tomasz Bober from Unimos Alliance quoted *“Duzgynelis is a great example of how a small, good idea could evolve into something much greater. From fresh, healthy food for kids they became an interesting example of SFSC for local community”*

5. MBUN (TURIN, ITALY)

Description

M**BUM (in Piedmontese dialect "Only Good") is a short supply chain agri-burger shop established in 2009. The raw material comes from the Scaglia Farm located in Rivoli (To), which has been breeding Piedmontese cattle since 1931 and in 1993 opened a corner shop. M**BUM uses only meat from animals raised on the farm with local corn, barley, wheat, and forage: Piedmontese cattle (450 head); pigs (180 head); chickens (4,000) and rabbits (600). The quality of the meat is recognized and certified as the farm is a member of the Consortium for the Protection of the Piedmontese Breed (Coalvi) and has recently obtained the recognition of the IGP "Vitellone Piemontese della Coscia". The farm is highly eco-sustainable and has invested in photovoltaics, to be energy independent for 8 months of the year.

Theme

Education and awareness-raising practices

Sector

Meat

IT

Website for ordering online delivery: [M**BUN | Agrihamburgeria Slow Fast Food a Torino e Rivoli \(mbun. it\)](https://www.agrihamburgeria.com)

Actors

Local suppliers

(<https://www.aziendaagricolascaglia.it/>)

and regional labelling stakeholders

(<https://www.coalvi.it/>)

Benefits

In the three M**Bun shops located in the metropolitan city of Turin, over 92% of purchases are made directly and without intermediaries from Piedmontese suppliers to ensure the quality and freshness of the product (sourdough bread, non-frozen potatoes, craft beer). Particular attention is paid to tradition, for example, the desserts are offered in "burnia" (jar) that can be taken home to reuse, and to sustainability: the use of disposable tableware made from biodegradable and fully compostable materials and a doggy bag is available for food not consumed. There is a dedicated menu for children, spaces for playing and informative material with an educational aim. M** BUM carries out activities of promotion and social development in the area, both by participating in charitable initiatives and by supporting associations that work on projects for charity.

Radio M**Bun, listenable also via the web, promotes the most interesting artists from Piedmont and relevant professionals, through live programs with guests and interaction with the listeners. The M**talent initiative is a music contest that has been bringing new musical talent to the stage for about four years. Quality, attention to sustainability and local products are the strong points that bring the producer closer to the consumer. The consumer can find all the information about the product on the blackboards displayed inside the stores and there is the opportunity to visit the farm to ensure producer-consumer contact.

It is a slow-fast food in which quality is the main value and it is shown in the people, clients, workers, and food.

agroBRIDGES insight

Patrizia Borsotto, from CREA quoted *“The M**BUN slow-fast food experience is an excellent way of promoting quality local products and bringing the consumer closer to the producer. Moreover, in contrast to the current trend of fast consumption, which isolates individuals and standardises food, this experiment in collective catering aims to create relationships and raise awareness of sustainable local production.”*

6. PODKARPACKIE SMAKI

(RZESZOW; POLAND)

Description

The PRO CARPATHIA - Association for the Development and Promotion of Podkarpacie is a business support organization created in 2004 and aimed at animating local communities and local governments.

One of them is the Subcarpathian Flavours Cluster - an association of local producers of traditional and organic regional food based on two criteria - quality and tradition. The cluster was established in January 2013 by 21 entities. Currently, it associates with 62 entities that gather producers of regional, traditional, and ecological products, restaurants, vineyards, confectioneries and agritourism farms.

It is also focused on the promotion of regional, traditional, and ecological products produced in the Podkarpackie Voivodeship, their promotion, as well as supporting the common culinary heritage of the region.

The organisation acts as a bridge to purchase products directly from producers and food processing companies. The first cluster activity was the creation of the Podkarpackie Tastes Culinary Trail - the only active culinary route in Podkarpacie and one of the longest culinary routes in Poland.

In several places on the Podkarpackie Tastes Culinary Trail, it is possible to find a specially prepared and labelled Podkarpackie Tastes Shelf, with regional, traditional and ecological products from local producers. The cluster also runs a stationary store with headquarters in the Regional Government Office.

In 2020, an online store was launched, followed by a retail store and warehouse located in Agrohurt - the agricultural commodity exchange. Both the on-line store and the stationary store offer fresh products directly from cluster members.

Theme

Mutual benefits between primary producers and consumers

Sector

All

Actors

Farmers, food producers and processors, local consumers, local authorities and regional government

IT

Online platform

<http://www.podkarpaciesmaki.pl/>

Benefits

Consumers can buy healthy products, traditional and organic. Products are labelled by the approved regional organisation. The online shop allows buying from home - which was important during the lockdown caused by covid-19.

agroBRIDGES insight

Tomasz Bober from Unimos Alliance quoted *“The Cluster’s activity adapted to the needs of consumers. Promotion of fresh, local products transformed to direct sales and on-line shop. They are raising customer’s awareness and supplying them with attractive products.*”

7. RECHTSTREEX (ROTTERDAM, NETHERLANDS)

Description

Rechtstreex provides an online platform where consumers can order local agri-food products. After the orders have been collected, local producers are informed and the food products are picked up and transported to the distribution centres from Rechtstreex. From there the products are sent to regional pick-up points where consumers can collect their orders.

Rechtstreex connects local farmers and producers with people who want to eat more consciously. In practice, that means a fair price for everyone, no food waste and transparency about where your food comes from. This applies both to the origin and production, and to how the price is arrived at. They want fresh and healthy food from the region to be accessible to everyone.

Theme

Mutual benefits between primary producers and consumers

Sector

All Sectors

IT

Webshop <https://www.rechtstreex.nl/>

Actors

Webshop developers / managers; producers; transporters; distribution centres; local distributors ("wijkchefs") and pick-up points

Benefits

An online platform with local pick-up points makes it easy for consumers to order a variety of locally produced food products and collect their orders in one-stop, close to their homes.

The main benefits for the producers are that they receive a higher share of the final selling price than when using conventional channels and they can increase their sales volume and reach consumers directly. For consumers, the main benefits are that they have access to locally produced food, can easily find information about the origin of the food and the producer via the Rechtstreex platform and they can pick up a variety of food products (fruits and vegetables, dairy products, meat etc.) from one pick-up point in their neighbourhood. The system also reduces food waste because deliveries are prepared based on the orders by consumers.

agroBRIDGES insight

Liesbeth Dries, from Wageningen University quoted *“The success of Rechtstreex is explained by it being a strongly demand-driven system, that benefits from combining convenience (of local pick-up points) with an extensive assortment (from engaging with multiple producers from different sectors)”*.

8. REKO FOOD COLLECTIVE (FINLAND)

Description

The REKO retail and distribution model is one of the most famous examples of a local food collective in Finland, that offers consumers a way of ordering products directly from the producer, without the need for middlemen. The REKO concept was established in Finland in 2012 and has spread to 14 countries and four different continents. The local REKO collectives operate via Facebook (FB) as closed groups in which orders and deliveries are agreed upon. Anyone can join the group on FB. Usually, there are a few consumers acting as moderators in the FB group. The moderators accept the consumers and producers who wish to join. The consumer and the producer/seller agree on the order in advance in the FB group and during the distribution event, the consumer goes to pick up and pay for the ordered product. Often, a larger number of households place an order for local food directly from the producer. The groups are run by volunteers, who do not receive payment for their contribution. The producer announces the goods that he/she sells in the FB group about a week before the distribution,

including the accepted method of payment and when the order will close. The notice specifies the price of each product. Buyers comment on the producer's sales announcement to state what products they want to order and what quantities they want. The agreement is binding for both parties. Orders are placed at varying intervals and can be picked up either from the producer or from a place agreed upon with the producer. Only products that have been pre-ordered in a closed FB group will be sold at the distribution.

Theme

Mutual benefits between primary producers and consumers

Sector

All

IT

Social media channels

Actors

Local farmers and food producers, consumers

Benefits

Farmers can interact directly with consumers, share their high-quality fresh products, and get a better price for their products. Consumers can easily purchase local (and organic) food, and buying directly from the producers (supporting the local small operators).

REKO collectives promote the demand and production of ethical, preferably organic or GMO-free, clean local food from small producers. REKO only sells food and direct by-products of food production. Only products that have been pre-ordered in a closed FB group will be sold at the distribution. The consumer and the producer/seller agree

on the order in advance in the FB group and during the distribution event, the consumer goes to pick up and pay for the ordered product.

Direct interaction with consumers and producers during distribution improves transparency and increases consumer trust. The products available must be clearly and fairly described on FB. For consumers, participation does not require regular subscriptions. The producer also does not have to offer their products at every distribution event. The activity is based on volunteering. The model brings local producers together and creates networks.

agroBRIDGES insight

Kaisa Vehmas and Minna Kulju from VTT quoted *“The REKO food collective is an easy way both for food producers and consumers to share / buy local food. In addition, the Covid-19 pandemic has increased consumers’ interest in environmentally friendly solutions and local and national products. Consumers are more and more willing to support local food producers.”*

9. SVAIGI (LATVIA)

Description

E-shop www.svaigi.lv is a cooperative shop of various small farmers and food producers from all over Latvia. In addition to food, it also offers organic cleaning supplies, cosmetics, packaging and products for pets. It is possible to order a regular delivery of various baskets (via a subscription-based model) with seasonal agricultural produce. Online shops have customer service channels (e-mail, telephone, chat apps, social media etc.). Customer relationship management takes place from a distance unless there are serious customer complaints that require face-to-face interaction. The idea is becoming more popular as digital solutions are becoming more prominent in food sales. Although face-to-face communication is part of sales culture, traditional farmers' markets have also partly employed digital solutions to tackle the impact of Covid-19.

Theme

Mutual benefits between primary producers and consumers

Sector

All Sectors

Actors

Farmers and e-shop. The company buys directly from farmers and sells to customers

IT

The online platform and social media

Benefits

Young professionals are looking for healthy and fresh food, but don't have time for traditional farmers' markets. Perfect timing with covid-19.

The model caters to the needs of urban residents as it allows them to get fresh produce without investing too much time by physically visiting farmers' markets or shops. Also, it is easy to make baskets with a range of products or choose already assembled baskets thus cutting downtime even more. In modern "lack of time" it is a good solution, that offers the same products as a farmers' market but 24/7 (with limited delivery times).

agroBRIDGES insight

Tomasz Bober from UNIMOS Alliance quoted *"SVAIGI combines tradition with modern technologies. It offers products from small farmers with the use of modern technology. Growing demand for organic products was one factor, another was COVID and the need to change the way of shopping. Being ready to face these challenges gave a chance to Svaigi on-line shop."*

10. TELARAKI (THESSALONIKI, GREECE)

Description

Telaraki.com is a new start-up based in Thessaloniki, Greece that sells high-quality and affordable fresh fruit and vegetables to local customers on a subscription basis. Customers can purchase subscription packages on the telaraki.com website to order fruit and vegetables regularly for a fixed price and have them delivered in wooden cases. Standard (one-time) orders of products are possible too. Customers can choose 4-12 items of fruit and vegetables from a wide variety of seasonal produce while an algorithm calculates quantities to match the subscription amount. The content of the order can be changed each week. Subscription packages include individual, couple and family packages.

Most fruit and vegetables are supplied from local wholesalers and are hand-picked to ensure the product is of supreme quality in terms of taste, and is aesthetically pleasing for consumers. To ensure that products are delivered in the freshest possible form to customers, the website accepts weekly orders and deliveries are carried out on standard days of the week.

In this way, storage needs and food waste are minimal. Moreover, packaging is made either from paper or wood to avoid environmental degradation from the use of plastics.

Sector

Fruit, vegetables, herbs

Theme

Mutual benefits between primary producers and consumers

IT

The startup is supported to a large degree by its website, as order placing, communications and sales are carried out mostly through the e-shop. The website contains smart features, especially concerning the subscription packages offered to clients, as an algorithm calculates produce quantities to ensure that clients stay within their subscription budget, based on their choice of products.

Actors

Wholesalers; Producers; Consumers; Website owners

Benefits

The startup intends to cover the needs of busy people, who don't have the time to pay frequent visits to the grocery store, as well as the needs of those who need to control the budget they spend on food. Moreover, most consumers don't know how to pick quality food themselves and thus benefit from the long-term experience the owners of telaraki.com have of working with fruits and vegetables.

Customers purchasing subscription packages benefit from having fresh seasonal fruit and vegetables selected for them based on quality, taste and durability and having them delivered at

home conveniently and without extra effort. Subscribers benefit from fixed unit prices for all products included in their delivery. The subscription-based sales model may offer the opportunity for distributors to plan efficiently the supply and delivery of products to customers, without having to invest in expensive preservation and storage equipment as they reach out to more clients.

In summary, Telaraki offers subscription-based sales and fixed prices of high-quality products for consumers. It is a user-friendly website enhanced with smart features. Telaraki ensures a minimum environmental footprint and food waste.

agroBRIDGES insight

George Malliopoulos and Eirini Efthymiadou from Q-PLAN quoted ***“Online shops for locally produced fresh food provide an excellent opportunity for Greek customers to reconnect with local producers, while having the benefits of easy and convenient shopping experience that is necessary for the needs of the average modern consumer.”***

11. LE CLOS FRÉMUR (FRANCE)

Description

The Clos Frémur farm has 4 hectares of an orchard with fertile, deep, and irrigated soils located at the confluence of the Loire and Maine rivers. Le Clos Frémur offers local baskets, which can be ordered online for weekly seasonal local products, or if preferred, there is a subscription option for recurring orders. They also have the option of renting out parts of the plot to consumers. In short, this business model proposes to make a plot a meeting and union place, thus promoting an educational and coexistence area of 500 m² for the members of the association and the subscribers.

Theme

Education and awareness-raising practices

Sector

All Sectors

Actors

Consumers, Producers

IT

Online website

Benefits

The objectives of the association "La Cueillette du Clos Frémur" are:

- Bring together conscious consumers who want to get involved in urban agricultural activity.
- Offer self-harvested seasonal vegetables and fruits to neighbourhood residents without intermediaries, at a fair price and without harvesting costs.
- Promote sustainable, socially equitable and ecologically sound agriculture.
- Strengthen social, intergenerational, and intercultural ties.

To make this plot a place of meeting and sharing, an **educational and convivial area** of 500 m² will be reserved for members of the association and subscribers.

agroBRIDGES insight

Pauline Bodin from VEGEPOLYS VALLEY quoted *"La cueillette du Clos Frémur is the simplest way to realise a SFSC as it is directly on the orchard, in direct contact with the product and the producer. For me, there is no better way to understand the value of the food than when you're picking it. This place leads to educating people on what they're eating, at a low price."*

12. WOMEN'S COOPERATIVES (TURKEY)

Description

Women's cooperatives produce local and domestic solutions to common problems faced especially under Covid-19 and play an important role in the development of SFSCs by creating social and economic values.

IT

PR activities will start as of April 2022

Sector

Private sector (fruit and vegetables), government and NGO (cooperatives)

Benefits

It is one of main tools available for promoting the SFSCs in Turkey, particularly for women taking an active leading role in this process. The primary target is to encourage women's entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector and to support the development of women farmers.

Theme

- A) Mutually benefits between producers and consumers
- b) Educational awareness or
- c) Public procurement SFSCs approaches

Actors

The works of the Kerevitaş firm can be shown as a best practice example from Turkey. Kerevitaş A.Ş was founded in the city of Bursa in 1970 and is a pioneer in frozen food production, as well as Turkey's first company in the frozen food retail sector. In 2021, the company started to work in cooperation with the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of the Republic of Turkey to provide women farmers with opportunities in the food supply chain. The top priority is to supply agricultural raw materials to the factory through the shortest supply chain network.

The province of Eskişehir was selected as the pilot province to cooperate primarily with women's agricultural cooperatives. Work has begun on contract agriculture and raw material procurement from female farmers working under the cooperatives. A working model was established to provide consultancy support to female farmers in all agricultural processes from seed support to harvest. The project will be carried out in cooperation with the public, NGO and private sectors.

agroBRIDGES insight

Begum Mutus from Sabri Ulker Vakfi quoted: *“The contract farming practice is based on the principle of guaranteed purchase, and is the model being expanded throughout Turkey. Supporting economic production from seed to harvest will encourage women entrepreneurs, and the support of expert agricultural engineers during the entire production process will pave the way for the dissemination of good agricultural practices throughout the country. The fact that the selected pilot regions are selected based on the principles of the shortest supply chain will support both environmental and economic development. Raising awareness as a good practice of these studies will create a ripple effect and will inspire other cooperatives and companies to encourage similar practices in the sector.”*

CONCLUSIONS

The 12 success cases outlined throughout this white paper highlight the many ways sustainable SFSC business models can be created. Some include e-commerce, digital engagement, making fast foods with local products or providing Food tourism. These are just a few examples of how you, as a farmer and brand owner, can be empowered to connect with the consumer to provide high-quality products and ensure sustainability in the long term for your business. The interactive catalogue with more examples of good practices and success cases can be found at [agroBRIGES website](#)([click here](#)).

Inspiring success cases are one of the best sharing collaborative initiatives to demonstrate the numerous options available to empower farmers' and producers' mission to deliver directly to society, and they can be used to encourage similar practices to be fine-tuned based on each region's characteristics.

We hope you've been inspired by these successful cases and if you are wondering if you will succeed, we truly believe **'YES YOU CAN!'**

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